

UNIVERSITI BRUNEI DARUSSALAM

MODULE: BM-5302 ORGANISATIONAL BEHAVIOUR

ASSIGNMENT:

REFLECTIVE ESSAY

TITLE:

**THE IMPORTANCE OF UNDERSTANDING ORGANISATIONAL BEHAVIOUR: A
REFLECTION ON FUTURE CAREER**

NAME: SITI NUR HAZIQAH BINTI LATIP

REG. NO.: 25M2949

Abstract

This reflective essay shows the importance of understanding organisational behaviour and to be applied in the workplace to provide different viewpoints on an individual's value and growth. This is through the perspectives of the national culture (Brunei) and the organisational culture in this case is UBD as my own experience. This helps to understand how various people communicate and behave in an organizational setting to improve communication, teamwork, leadership and prevent misunderstandings. In Brunei's culture, respect and ethical responsibilities are the main points that play a huge role in a future workplace. Meanwhile, for UBD's organizational culture looks at the academic motivation, teamwork and, communication is crucial to promote growth, adapting and to a successful future. Therefore, this paper includes the reason of my interest to join this module, my own experiences and opinion as to how it helps shaped my perspective on my future career, and the two different perspectives from Brunei's culture and the UBD's culture.

The reason I had chosen BM-5302: Organisational Behaviour as my optional module is because I think knowing people's behaviour, understand and anticipate in a workplace behaviour is essential for my future career. It can be important as it will help to understand and know why certain people act and behave in a workplace which helps to boost organizational efficacy and improve worker satisfaction. Additionally, I have a degree in Accounting and Finance and I am thinking of working in one of the audit firms in Brunei.

In addition, as I was an intern in an audit firm previously, I had learned that being an auditor, it is important to have constant communication with the clients to gather information and work well together with my team members to accomplish the tasks given. Also, by respecting the seniors by doing my given tasks and listen to their advices. Therefore, by taking this module, I can improve my communication skills, learn how to work better in a team, avoid conflict, and how to be professional at work.

In my perspective of national culture in Brunei, following the four cultural values, which is respect, not offending others, minding your own business and the pro-seniority culture (Idris, 2021). I believe it is important in Brunei to have these cultures to shape my values and career wise. I was taught in a young age to do so and it has shaped my values until today. In Brunei, respecting other people especially elderlies or seniors in a workplace is important to maintain a good relationship and enhance responsibility in a workplace. Therefore, these National Cultures helps me to respect one another as well as promoting harmony and ethical behaviour in my future job.

Furthermore, the organizational culture in UBD is the encouragement of lifelong learning, being kind to others, teamwork, and motivating students towards academic success to help students gain knowledge and prepare for their future career. I think understanding the behavioral culture in UBD helps me to communicate well with people around me and adapt well with the new surroundings.

For example, through group discussions in class, group activities, PMUBD clubs helps me to collaborate and meet new people and gain new skills to help with communicating and being exposed to other cultures. Therefore, UBD promotes harmony, increase my culture awareness and develop my social skills that is important for self growth.

Reference

Idris, P. S. R. P. H. (2021). Cultural Values and Its Influence on the Enactment of Leadership in Public Sector Organisations. *International Journal of Asian Business and Information Management*, 12(4), 1–19. <https://doi.org/10.4018/ijabim.20211001.oa1>